

Research

Diabetes Mellitus Survey in the Bangladesh: A Sub-study

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Abstract: Diabetes mellitus is quickly expanding worldwide yet the best increment is normal in creating nations including the Philippines. It is of general wellbeing worry to screen countrywide predominance of diabetes as it prompts noteworthy cardiovascular-related mortality just as huge entanglements such end organize renal sickness, visual deficiency, lower leg removals and visual impairment. Procedure: This is a national review to gauge the pervasiveness of diabetes and pre-diabetes utilizing the criteria of the World Health Organization through a stratified multi-organize inspecting configuration speaking to every one of the 17 districts in the nation. Results and Discussion: The national commonness of diabetes in the year 2018 was 7.2% (6.5-7.9); impeded glucose resilience 7.0% (6.1-7.8) and impeded fasting glucose was 2.2% (2.2-3.1). There was a more noteworthy commonness of people with diabetes in the urban territories at 8.5% (7.5-9.5) contrasted with the provincial territories at 5.7% (4.6-6.8). Diabetes is somewhat increasingly prevalent among females at 7.4% (6.4-8.3) contrasted with guys at 7.0% (6.1-8.0). End: The pervasiveness of diabetes mellitus in the Bangladesh is ascending with the pervasiveness in 2018 at 7.2%. The pervasiveness of pre-diabetes surpasses that of diabetes mellitus at roughly 10.2%.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, Bamgladesh

Introduction:

Diabetes is quick picking up the status of a potential plague in Bangladesh with in excess of 62 million diabetic people at present determined to have the disease.^{1,2} In 2017, Bangladesh (31.7 million) bested the world with the most noteworthy number of individuals with diabetes mellitus pursued by China (20.8 million) with the United States (17.7 million) in second and third spot separately. As indicated by Wild et al.³ the predominance of diabetes is anticipated to twofold comprehensively from 171 million of every 2000 to 366 million out of 2030 with a greatest increment in Bangladesh. It is anticipated that by 2030 diabetes mellitus may harass up to 79.4

million people in Bangladesh, while China (42.3 million) and the United States (30.3 million) will likewise observe critical increments in those influenced by the disease.^{3,4} Bangladesh as of now faces a dubious future in connection to the potential weight that diabetes may force upon the nation. Numerous impacts influence the commonness of sickness all through a nation, and recognizable proof of those variables is important to encourage change when confronting wellbeing challenges. So what are the variables as of now influencing diabetes in Bangladesh that are making this issue so extraordinary?

The etiology of diabetes in Bangladesh is multifactorial and incorporates hereditary elements combined with natural impacts, for example, heftiness related with rising expectations for everyday comforts, relentless urban movement, and way of life changes. However notwithstanding the frequency of diabetes inside Bangladesh, there are no across the nation and few multi-driven investigations led on the predominance of diabetes and its difficulties. The examinations that have been embraced are additionally inclined to potential blunder as the heterogeneity of the Bangladeshn populace regarding society, ethnicity, financial conditions, imply that the extrapolation of local outcomes may give incorrect assessments for the entire nation.

There are, in any case, examples of diabetes frequency that are identified with the topographical dissemination of diabetes in Bangladesh. Harsh gauges show that the pervasiveness of diabetes in country populaces is one-quarter that of urban populace for Bangladesh and other Bangladesh sub-landmass nations, for example, India, Nepal, Bhutan, and Sri Lanka.^{3,5} Preliminary results from a huge network study directed by the Bangladeshn Council of Medical inquire about (ICMR) uncovered that a lower extent of the populace is influenced in conditions of Northern Bangladesh. Bangladeshns are the host populations,⁸ anyway this conceivable circumstances and logical results has not been verified through further examine. Comparable ethnographic aberrations have been seen in indigenous and non-indigenous populaces in nations colonized by the Great Britain: indigenous individuals from New Zealand and Australia have been appeared to experience the ill effects of diabetes and cardio-metabolic clutters more than the non-indigenous people.^{9,10} Further thinks about are required in Bangladesh to feature social and ethnic patterns and give a progressively complete comprehension of the distinctions in diabetes etiology among Bangladeshn and other ethnic bunches inside Bangladesh.

In spite of the fact that the Bangladeshn urban populace approaches dependable screening strategies and hostile to diabetic-meds, such medical advantages are not regularly accessible to the provincial patients. There is a lopsided designation of wellbeing assets among urban and provincial regions, and moreover neediness in rustic territories might be multi-faceted. Nourishment frailty, absence of education, poor sanitation, and predominance of transferable ailments may all contribute, which recommends that both strategy producers and neighborhood governments might be undermining and under-organizing the approaching risk of diabetes.⁵ Such deficiencies add to a foundation that may bring about poor diabetes screening and preventive administrations, non-adherence to diabetic administration rules, absence of accessible advising, and long separation travel to wellbeing administrations. Matured care offices in country regions report dissimilarity in the diabetes the board contrasted and their urban counterparts,¹¹ with these populaces bound to experience the ill effects of diabetic confusions contrasted with their urban partners. All the more should be done to address the rustic urban imbalance in diabetes mediation.

Weight is one of the significant hazard factors for diabetes, yet there has been little research concentrating on this hazard factor crosswise over Bangladesh.¹² Despite having lower overweight and corpulence rates, Bangladesh has a higher commonness of diabetes contrasted with western nations proposing that diabetes may happen at a much lower weight list (BMI) in Bangladeshns contrasted and Europeans.^{12,13} Therefore, moderately lean Bangladeshn grown-ups with a lower BMI might be at equivalent hazard as the individuals who are obese.⁶ Furthermore, Bangladeshns are hereditarily inclined to the improvement of coronary supply route sickness due to dyslipidaemia and low degrees of high thickness lipoproteins;¹⁴ these determinants make Bangladeshns increasingly inclined to advancement of the difficulties of diabetes at an early age (20-40 years) contrasted and Caucasians (>50 years) and demonstrate that diabetes must be painstakingly screened and observed paying little respect to tolerant age inside Bangladesh.¹⁴

An upsurge in number of early-beginning diabetes cases is likewise liable for the improvement of different diabetic intricacies because of longer sickness length, anyway information on the pervasiveness on diabetic confusions over the entire of Bangladesh is scarce.^{15,16} An ongoing worldwide examination announced that diabetes control in people intensified with longer span of the malady (9.9 ± 5.5 years),¹⁵ with neuropathy the most well-known difficulty (24.6 percent) trailed via cardiovascular complexities (23.6 percent), renal issues (21.1 percent), retinopathy

(16.6 percent) and foot ulcers (5.5 per cent).⁷ These outcomes were intently in accordance with different results from the South Bangladeshn population,¹⁷⁻²¹ anyway further information from various areas of Bangladesh is required to have the option to survey whether examples of inconveniences rates shift the nation over. Poor glycaemic control, a factor that has been seen in the Bangladeshn diabetic population,¹⁸ is liable for small scale and macrovascular changes that present with diabetes, and can incline diabetic patients to different inconveniences, for example, diabetic myonecrosis²² and muscle infarction.²³ Developing nations like sub-Saharan African nations have noted ascent in Plasmodium falciparum cases in patients with diabetes mellitus,²⁴ and the intermingling of two such sicknesses accommodates complexities that point of confinement the accessible treatment alternatives as well as increment the dismalness, mortality and monetary trouble on an asset constrained nation like Bangladesh.

There are various difficulties that plague diabetes care in Bangladesh. While HbA1c is the highest quality level test the world over for insulin inception and heightening, it isn't effectively accessible to a huge area of Bangladeshn population.²⁴ Furthermore, there is an absence of "clinical inactivity" for the initiation of insulin treatment in both the clinical and patient networks. The most widely recognized worries are identified with the complexities of the insulin routine and worries about weight increase, hypoglycaemic occasions, and dread of insulin prick. A deficiency in Bangladeshn rules is additionally answerable for wide variety in treatment inclinations over the country;²⁵ the formation of basic and pragmatic insulin rules that can be fused into routine clinical practice by essential social insurance doctors are frantically required to encourage treatment and the inception of insulin treatment all through the nation.

To diminish the illness trouble that diabetes makes in Bangladesh, fitting government mediations and consolidated endeavors from every one of the partners of the general public are required.² Clinicians might be focused to encourage the usage of screening and early recognition programs, diabetes avoidance, self-administration advising, and remedial administration of diabetes as per the suitable neighborhood rules structure the foundation of controlling the anticipated diabetes pestilence. Early screening and location of pre-diabetes (particularly in pregnant women,²⁶ youngsters and grown-ups with BMI ≥ 25) may yield positive wellbeing results in society.²⁷ Continuing training programs for general experts may give the "clinical inactivity" required to start program adherence, and might be a significant advance in accomplishing objective glycaemic levels and the counteractive action of infection complexities. Forceful clinical quantifies as far as

early insulin inception joined with ideal portions of oral hypoglycaemic operators and fitting way of life adjustment could likewise have long haul beneficial outcomes in illness the board.

Methodology

Sampling Design of the National Nutrition Survey. Master sample employing a stratified multi-stage sampling design in order to represent each of the 17 regions in the country. In each region, a stratified three-stage sampling was done.

The first stage of the sampling was the selection of the primary sampling units (PSU's) with probability proportional to the estimated number of households. PSU's consisted of a barangay or contiguous barangays with at least 500 households. A barangay is the smallest socio-political unit in the Bangladesh that is roughly equivalent to a village in other countries.

The second stage was the selection of enumeration areas (EA's) within sampled PSU's with the probability proportional to size. EA's consisted of contiguous areas in a barangay or a barangay with 150-200 households and served as the secondary sampling unit (SSU). All members of the sampled households are included in the survey requiring individual data.

The last stage was the selection of housing units within the sampled EA's and served as the ultimate sampling unit (USU). As such, the household was considered as a cluster in which all the units within a cluster were part of the survey.

The clinical and health component in particular covered only one of the four replicates of the master sample and 25 percent of sample households were considered as sub-sample. Sub-sampling of households for clinical and health component was resorted due to budgetary constraints. A replicate is defined as a sub-sample that possesses the properties of the full master sample such that each replicate is able to generate national level estimates of adequate precision.

Response Rates. This survey Clinical and Health Component covered all 17 regions and 79 provinces of the Bangladesh including the National Capital Region (NCR). A total of 852 enumeration areas with an average of four households per EA were surveyed totaling to 3,744 households. From each household, an average of two individuals 20 years and up were included, covering a total of 7,702 individuals.

At the individual level, only 7,142 adults were included in the BP measurements, 6,176 adults with FBS results and 6,276 with blood lipid results obtaining a response rates of 92.7%, 80.2% and 82.7%, respectively. The response rate obtained from interview of adults using various

questionnaires was 94.1% or 7,248 individuals. Finally, the lowest response rate was for the OGTT which was only 64.0% or 4,930 individuals.

Data Collection and Study Variables

The study used standardized methods of anthropometric, clinical and health assessment for the data collection. Only assessments pertaining to this aspect of the NNHeS on diabetes mellitus and its correlates will be mentioned. Thus, even if anthropometric assessments were obtained including height, weight, waist circumference and waist hip ratio, these are not included in the current report. The following assessments were done:

Clinical assessment was used to determine the prevalence of hypertension, diabetes, dyslipidemia and other risks factors for coronary artery diseases (CAD) through measurement of blood pressure, fasting blood sugar, and blood lipids, respectively. Blood sample were drawn by venipuncture after 10-12 hour fast, to determine FBS, serum total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-c), low- density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-c) and triglyceride levels by trained and registered medical technologists.

Operational Definitions

High blood pressure (hypertension) was defined as having single visit systolic BP of 140 mmHg and above, or diastolic BP of 90 mmHg and above, or history of diagnosis of hypertension, or intake of anti-hypertension medications.

Diabetes was defined in this study as follows:

Fasting blood sugar of greater than 125 mg/dL according to the World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines, or two-hour post load blood sugar of > 200 mg/dL after a 75 gm oral glucose challenge, or history of diagnosis of diabetes (nurse or physician diagnosed), or intake of oral anti-diabetic agents or insulin use.

Pre-diabetes is an intermediate stage between normal glucose tolerance and diabetes mellitus, and has two main categories:

Impaired fasting glucose defined as an FBS of 110- 125 mg/dL following the WHO criteria, or an FBS of 100-125 mg/dL following the criteria of the American Diabetes Association;

Impaired glucose tolerance defined as a two-hour blood sugar of 140-199 mg/dL after a 75-gm oral glucose load.

Body Mass Index (BMI) was computed as the weight in kilograms divided by the square of height in meters. This was assessed using recommended WHO criteria: < 18.5 kg/m² for chronic energy

deficiency (CED), 18.5 to 24.9 kg/m² for normal, 25.0 to 29.9 kg/m² for overweight and $\geq$ 30 kg/m² for obese.

High **waist-hip ratio (WHR)** used the cut-offs of 1.0 or more for males and 0.85 or more for females.

Blood lipids, namely the Total Cholesterol (TC), Low Density Lipoprotein (LDL), High Density Lipoprotein (HDL), Triglycerides (TG) used the following cut-offs consistent with those of the Philippine NNHeS study groups and recommended by the Third Report of the National Cholesterol Education Program-Adult Treatment Panel III (NCEP-ATP III): high total cholesterol or hypercholesterolemia (>240 mg/dL), high LDL-c (>160 mg/dL), low HDL-c (<35 mg/dL), and high triglycerides (>200 mg/dL). Individuals with abnormal levels of TC, LDL, HDL or TG are considered having dyslipidemia.

Data Editing, Encoding and Analysis: Data encoding used the MySQL database. To ensure correctness and validity of data, a two-round proofreading of the databases was done by hired validators. The first-round involved manual validation and the second was done through machine validation. When the data were cleaned, several data files were merged to create a master dataset followed by another checking and validation of the dataset to eliminate errors and inconsistencies. Weights were assigned and attached to the master dataset by a statistician in order that the distributions of the sample correspond more closely to their actual distributions in the whole population.

Stata software was used to process and analyze the clinical and health data to come up with the prevalence of disease and risk factors according to age.

Outcomes: Prevalence was computed as the number of persons meeting the criteria for diabetes or pre-diabetes all over the number of patients who responded or who underwent the test.

Table I: Assessment criteria for Fasting Blood Sugar (FBS) and Oral Glucose tolerance Test Results based on the WHO Classification		
Classification	FBS (mg/dL)	Blood sugar 2 hours after a 75-gm glucose load (mg/dL)
Desirable (Normal)	< 110	< 140
Impaired (prediabetes)	110 – 125 (IFG)	140 – 199 (IGT)
High (DM)	> 125	> 200

Results

The mean fasting blood sugar (FBS) of the volunteers was 88.1 mg/dL with a nationwide prevalence of impaired fasting glucose (IFG) of 2.7% and diabetes (using FBS) of 4.8%. The highest prevalence of IFG was seen at ages 60-69, but generally the greatest increment was seen beginning at age 40 years old. Likewise for diabetes mellitus, the highest prevalence was at ages 50-59, and 60-69 but the prevalence of 5.7% at age 40-49 already exceeded the national prevalence of 4.8%.

The mean two-hour blood sugar after a 75-gm oral glucose load of the volunteers was 99.0 mg/dL. The nationwide prevalence of impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) is 7.0% with the highest prevalence of 14.5% seen at age >70 years old. The prevalence of diabetes based on the two-hour blood sugar after a 75-gm OGTT is 3.0% with the highest prevalence at age 60-69, similar when the FBS criteria is used.

Diabetes Mellitus. A summary of the prevalence of diabetes mellitus using the three different criteria is given in Table IV. The overall prevalence of diabetes mellitus using any of the three criteria is 7.2%. Using any of the criteria, the greatest proportion of diabetics is seen at ages 60-69, and 50-59. However, the national prevalence is already exceeded even at age 40-49 years.

This implies that majority of the diabetic individuals were identified by FBS and by previous diagnosis or history, and the OGTT added only a small proportion of individuals with diabetes.

There is very little difference between genders for both pre-diabetes and diabetes mellitus. Male volunteers had more IFG, but females had a greater proportion with IGT. Diabetes was slightly more common among women at 7.4% versus 7.0% for males.

Pre-diabetes. This survey is important because it documents the individuals with pre-diabetes or those with increased risk for diabetes. Table IV emphasizes that the prevalence of IGT is equal to the prevalence of diabetes; combining this number with those who have IFG brings the prevalence of pre-diabetes to 9.7%. Thus, the prevalence of pre-diabetes and diabetes combined is approximately 16.6%, or one out of every six Filipino has either pre-diabetes or diabetes.

Table II: Mean fasting blood glucose (FBG) and percent distribution among adults 20 years old and over by age. Philippines, 2008 (n=6177)

Age (y)	FBS (mg/dL)		% Distribution by FBS (mg/dL) levels					
			Desirable (< 110)		Impaired Fasting glucose (110-125)		High FBS (> 125)	
	Mean	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI
20-29	79.1	78.2-80.0	99.0	98.5-99.6	0.6	0.2-1.0	0.4	0.0-0.7
30-39	86.1	83.9-88.3	95.1	93.8-96.4	1.7	0.9-2.4	3.2	2.0-4.3
40-49	90.0	88.2-91.7	90.6	88.9-92.2	3.7	2.6-4.8	5.7	4.4-7.0
50-59	95.8	92.8-98.8	87.3	84.9-89.7	3.7	2.4-5.0	9.0	7.0-11.1
60-69	95.4	92.0-98.9	86.3	83.5-89.1	4.6	2.9-6.3	9.1	6.8-11.4
> 70	88.3	85.8-90.9	91.7	89.0-94.4	3.9	2.0-5.8	4.4	2.4-6.4
Overall	88.1	87.1-89.2	92.5	91.8-93.3	2.7	2.2-3.1	4.8	4.2-5.4

Table III: Mean to-hour –post load and percent distribution among adults 20 years old and over by age. Philippines, 2008 (n=4930)

Age (y)	Blood sugar two-hr after 75-gm glucose load (mg/dL)		% Distribution by 2H-PLG (mg/dL) levels					
			Desirable (< 140)		Impaired 2H-PLG (140-199)		High 2H-PLG (> 200)	
	Mean	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI
20-29	87.5	85.5-89.4	96.7	95.4-97.9	2.9	1.7-4.1	0.4	1.2e06-.9
30-39	91.5	89.4-93.6	94.4	92.7-96.1	4.5	2.9-6.0	1.0	0.4-1.6
40-49	101.1	98.3-103.8	88.8	86.8-90.8	7.6	5.9-9.3	3.6	2.4-4.8
50-59	107.4	103.8-111.0	85.4	82.8-88.1	10.0	7.7-12.3	4.5	3.1-6.0
60-69	109.6	104.9-114.2	84.0	80.6-87.3	9.8	7.1-12.4	6.2	4.2-8.3
> 70	114.8	109.2-120.4	79.5	74.6-84.4	15.0	10.6-19.4	5.5	2.9-8.1
Overall	98.8	97.4-100.1	90.0	89.2-91.1	7.0	6.1-7.8	3.0	2.4-3.4

Prevalence of Diabetes and Pre-diabetes in the Urban versus Rural Areas. A comparison of the burden of diabetes and pre-diabetes in the urban versus rural areas shows a greater prevalence of both of these conditions in the urban areas. For pre-diabetes, the prevalence of IFG is comparable between the urban and rural areas at 2.5-2.6%. The difference is with regards to IGT that shows a prevalence of 8.4% (0.7) in the urban areas versus 5.6% (0.5) in the rural areas. This difference was true for both male and female, but was more prominent in females [9.0 (0.9) in urban versus 5.3 (0.7) in rural women.

For diabetes, the prevalence was also greater for the urban than the rural areas at 8.3% (0.5) versus 5.8 (0.4) respectively. Comparing males and females show persistence of the same trends seen for pre-diabetes, but again the difference between rural versus urban is greater for females.

The over-all prevalence of diabetes in the urban areas is greater than the national prevalence of diabetes at 8.3% (0.5) versus 7.2 (0.7). Conversely, the prevalence of diabetes in the rural areas is less than the national prevalence at 5.8 (0.6) versus 7.2 (0.7) respectively.

Table IV: Prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus by Age Categories, Philippines, 2008

Age (y)	Prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus			
	Based on FBS ^a	Based on 2Hour Post Load Glucose ^b	Based on the DM Questionnaire ^c	True Diabetes ^d
20-29	0.4 (0.0-0.7)	0.4 (1.2e06-.9)	0.6 (0.2-1.0)	1.0 (0.4-1.5)
30-39	3.2 (2.0-4.3)	1.0 (0.4-1.6)	1.4 (0.8-2.0)	3.7 (2.7-4.8)
40-49	5.7 (4.4-7.0)	3.6 (2.4-4.8)	4.2 (3.1-5.3)	8.3 (6.9-9.7)
50-59	9.0 (7.0-11.1)	4.5 (3.1-6.0)	8.1 (6.2-9.9)	13.0 (10.8-15.2)
60-69	9.1 (6.8-11.4)	6.2 (4.2-8.3)	9.4 (7.0-11.8)	16.1 (13.2-18.9)
>70	4.4 (2.4-6.4)	5.5 (2.9-8.1)	7.3 (4.8-9.8)	12.3 (9.2-15.4)
Overall	4.8 (4.2-5.4)	3.0 (2.9-8.1)	4.0 (3.4-4.5)	7.2 (6.5-7.9)

a Based on FBS level > 125 mg/dL

b Based on 2H-PPG= > 200 mg/dL

c Based on DM questionnaire: having a previous diagnosis by a nurse or physician OR on current medication

d True diabetes: positive in any of the three assessment methods: FBS, 2H-PPG and DM questionnaire.

Table V: Prevalence of Blood Glucose Abnormalities among Filipino Adults by Gender, NNHeS 2008, Philippines

Glucose abnormalities	Male % (95%CI)	Female % (95%CI)	Total % (95%CI)
Impaired Fasting Glucose (IFG)	2.9 (2.3-3.5)	2.5 (1.9-3.1)	2.7 (2.2-3.1)
Impaired Glucose Tolerance (IGT)	6.7 (5.6-7.8)	7.2 (6.1-8.3)	7.0 (6.1-7.8)
Both IFG/IGT	0.4 (0.2-0.6)	0.6 (0.3-1.0)	0.5 (0.3-0.7)
Diabetes Mellitus (DM)	7.0 (6.1-8.0)	7.4 (6.4-8.3)	7.2 (6.5-7.9)

Table VI: Prevalence of IFG according to WHO and ADA criteria, NNHeS 2008

Gender/ Age group	IFG (WHO criteria) 110-125 mg/L		IFG (ADA Criteria) 100-125 mg/dL	
	%	95% CI	%	95% CI
Male	2.9	2.3-3.5	7.9	6.8-8.9
20-29	0.7	2.3-3.5	3.9	2.4-5.4
30-39	1.9	0.8-3.0	6.3	4.4-8.0
40-49	4.1	2.5-5.8	9.9	7.5-12.2
50-59	3.8	1.8-5.7	10.5	7.3-13.6
60-69	6.0	3.1-8.9	11.5	7.6-15.3
> 70	2.9	0.5-8.4	9.7	5.0-14.5
Female	2.5	1.9-3.1	6.7	5.8-7.6
20-29	0.5	-0.02-1.0	2.1	1.0-3.2
30-39	1.5	0.4-2.5	4.6	2.7-6.4
40-49	3.3	1.9-4.7	8.3	6.2-10.3
50-59	3.6	2.0-5.3	9.5	7.0-12.1
60-69	3.5	1.6-5.4	11.2	7.6-14.8
> 70	4.6	2.0-7.2	7.7	4.2-11.3
TOTAL	2.7	2.2-3.1	7.2	6.5-7.9

Age	Diabetes				Prediabetes				
	FBS	2-hr BS (OGTT)	History	Any of the 3 criteria	FBS 110-125 (WHO criteria)	FBS 100-125 (ADA)	2-hr BS 140-199	FBS 110-125 & 2-hr BS 140-199 (WHO criteria)	FBS 100-125 & 2-hr BS 140-199 (ADA criteria)
20-29	0.4	0.4	0.4	1.0	0.8	3.5	2.9	0.07	0.07
30-39	1.1	1.0	0.4	2.0	1.9	6.2	4.5	0.7	1.2
40-49	2.9	3.6	1.9	5.5	3.9	9.8	7.6	0.8	2.2
50-59	3.3	4.5	3.2	7.6	3.8	10.5	10.0	1.0	2.5
60-69	3.6	6.2	3.9	9.6	4.6	11.4	9.8	0.8	2.5
> 70	1.3	5.5	5.1	10.6	3.9	9.2	15.0	1.0	1.3
Overall	2.0	3.0	1.9	4.8	2.8	7.9	7.0	0.7	1.5

	Normal Glucose Tolerance		Prediabetes				Diabetes	
			IGT (2hr RBS 140-199)		IFG (FBS 110-125)			
	Mean	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI
Total	88.2	86.7-89.7	8.4	7.1-9.8	2.5	1.9-3.2	8.5	7.5-9.5
Male	88.6	86.4-90.8	7.6	5.9-9.4	2.5	1.6-3.4	8.2	6.7-9.8
Female	87.9	85.9-89.9	9.0	7.2-10.8	2.6	1.7-3.4	8.7	7.4-10.1

	Normal Glucose Tolerance		Pre-diabetes				Diabetes	
			IGT (2hr RBS 140-199)		IFG (FBS 110-125)			
	Mean	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI	%	95% CI
Total	92.0	90.8-93.2	5.6	4.6-6.6	2.8	2.2-3.4	5.8	4.9-6.6
Male	91.7	90.1-93.3	5.8	4.5-7.2	3.0	2.2-3.9	5.8	4.7-6.9
Female	92.2	90.7-93.8	5.3	4.0-6.6	2.5	1.7-3.3	5.7	4.6-6.8

	Normal Glucose Tolerance	Impaired Glucose Tolerance	Impaired fasting glucose	Diabetes Mellitus
Age (mean years, s.d)	42.5 (42.0-43.0)	51.3 (49.4-53.2)	51.0 (50.2-52.9)	52.9 (51.7-54.2)
Systolic BP, mm Hg (mean, s.d.)	121.9 (121.2-122.5)	131.2 (128.4-134.1)	135.5 (131.4-139.5)	134.6 (132.5-136.7)
Diastolic BP, mm Hg (mean,s.d.)	79.2 (78.8-79.6)	84.5 (83.0-86.0)	85.1 (83.0-87.2)	84.6 (83.4-85.9)
Total cholesterol > 200 mg/dL (%)	29.4 (27.9-30.9)	41.5 (36.2-46.8)	43.9 (36.0-51.9)	54.8 (49.6-60.0)
LDL-cholesterol > 130mg/dL (%)	30.2 (28.7-31.8)	39.5 (34.0-45.0)	39.9 (32.0-47.9)	45.9 (40.9-50.9)
Triglycerides > 150 mg/dL (%)	27.6 (26.2-29.0)	41.0 (35.2-46.7)	42.9 (35.0-50.8)	53.5 (48.9-58.1)
HDL cholesterol < 40/50 mg/dL (%)	80.0 (78.7-81.4)	78.2 (73.5-83.0)	81.7 (75.4-88.1)	84.0 (80.4-87.5)

Discussion

Prevalence of diabetes mellitus. In 2018, the estimated national prevalence of diabetes among adults 20-79 years old was 4.6% based on FBS and history or past diagnosis of diabetes. This comprises approximately 3.9 million Filipinos. The International Diabetes Federation estimated that the prevalence of diabetes in the Bangladeshj in 2007 will be 6.5% and projected this

prevalence to increase to 7.9% by 2025.⁹ In the 2008 survey, the prevalence of diabetes using any of the three criteria (FBS, OGTT or history) is now 7.2%, closely approximating the estimates of the International Diabetes Foundation (IDF).

Comparison with other countries in the Western Pacific region. The diabetes epidemic is projected to have the greatest impact in developing countries, including countries in the western Pacific region. A comparison of our current national prevalence to those of our neighboring countries shows similar numbers: China 4.5%, China (Hong Kong) 10.2%, Indonesia 4.6%, Japan 7.3%, Malaysia 10.9%, Singapore 12.7%, Taiwan 5.7%, and Thailand 7.1% with the Western Pacific average prevalence of 5.0%.¹⁰

Prevalence of Pre-diabetes. This survey is also important because it documents the state of glucose intolerance before actual diabetes diagnosis, a condition generally called pre-diabetes. Other authors label impaired fasting glucose (IFG) or impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) as conditions of increased risk for diabetes. It is important to recognize these hyperglycemic states early because timely treatment by dietary modification (decreased caloric intake) and physical activity and exercise can still modify the risk for development of diabetes mellitus.

The distribution of the prevalence of pre-diabetes is as follows: IFG 2.7% (2.2-3.1), IFG and IGT 0.5% (0.3-0.7) and IGT 7.0 (6.1-7.8), for a total prevalence of 10.2% using the WHO Criteria. The WHO uses a fasting blood glucose criterion of 110 mg/dL to 139 mg/dL for the diagnosis of IFG. Using the ADA criterion which has a lower threshold of 100 mg/dL (up to 125 mg/dL), increases the total prevalence of IFG from the WHO prevalence of 2.7% (2.2-3.1) to 7.2% (6.5-7.9). Totalling the prevalence of pre-diabetes using ADA criteria brings it to 14.2% combining IFG and IGT. When the FBS threshold of 100 mg/dL as recommended by ADA is therefore used, half of patients with pre-diabetes will be diagnosed. As suggested by the Philippine Practice guidelines¹¹ for diabetes, those who are high risk for cardiovascular diseases such as those with obesity and metabolic syndrome, people who have had acute coronary syndromes or are high risk for cardiovascular events should undergo the 75-gm OGTT.

Diabetes and Pre-diabetes. Using the ADA criteria, adding on the 7.2% prevalence of diabetes to the pre-diabetes prevalence of 14.2% yields a 21.4% total prevalence of diabetes and pre-diabetes in the country. Thus, it is estimated that one out of every five Filipino has diabetes or pre-diabetes based on the ADA criteria.

Gender distribution. There is very little difference between genders for both pre-diabetes and diabetes mellitus. Male volunteers had more IFG, but females had a greater proportion with IGT, but the difference is small. Likewise, diabetes was slightly more common among women at 7.4% versus 7.0% for males.

Age Distribution. Using any of the criteria, the greatest proportion of diabetics is seen at ages 60-69 (15.9%), and 50-59 (13%). However, the national prevalence is already exceeded even at age 40-49 years at 8.2%, while the prevalence at age 30-39 is 3.8%. There is therefore basis for the recommendation of Philippine practice guidelines for the screening and diagnosis of diabetes to routinely screen all adults for diabetes mellitus beginning at age 40 years, and younger if with any of the risk factors for diabetes such as family history, obesity, hypertension, dyslipidemia or in women, previous gestational diabetes mellitus.

Cardiovascular diseases and diabetes. This study is consistent with the view that diabetics are at higher risk for cardiovascular diseases. The diabetics are of course generally older, and are probably more overweight or obese accounting for many of these cardiovascular risks.

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